

What will affect future Scottish arable and horticulture production? Identifying drivers of change with agricultural stakeholders

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Study synopsis

The cereal, fruit and potato sectors contribute significantly to the Scottish economy. The future sustainability of agricultural production in Scotland and globally is under pressure from environmental stresses (soil degradation, pest and diseases, climate stress) and influenced by economic and political factors. The **overall aim** of this research is to work with agricultural stakeholders to explore what might happen to arable and horticultural production in Scotland in the future and by doing so, raise awareness, stimulate creative thinking, and gain insights about the influence between the social, economic and environmental drivers. Through plausible accounts we will explore future possibilities with stakeholders rather than make forecasts. By looking at past and present events, this exercise will help identify avenues which are robust, flexible but imperfect guides to unpredictable future events and prepare for and prevent future threats. The study is carried out in two stages, the first of which is reported here.

The **first objective** was to work with stakeholders to characterise and prioritise key threats to the sustainability of key Scottish agriculture sectors. Information was gathered using an online survey distributed to agricultural stakeholders (farmers, agronomists, crop breeders, scientists, policy advisors, regulatory bodies, and value chain actors) supplemented by face-to-face discussion groups at relevant stakeholder events. The results indicated that increasing pest and disease incidence, particularly due to more favourable climatic conditions and decreasing availability of pesticides, are viewed as a major threat to future crop production. Additional high priority drivers included global conflict and financial pressures through increased costs, and the effects of EU Exit and national policy on labour availability, export regulation and market globalisation.

The information gathered from the survey will be used to inform the second stage of the research in the coming year, to address the **second objective** of co-developing future scenarios of threats (and opportunities) to agricultural production and analysing these with stakeholders to co-construct flexible guides for safeguarding the future of the cereal, fruit and potato sectors.

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Background

The changing climate, pest and disease pressures, and national and global events can affect the productivity of agriculture and trade in agricultural goods. One way to mitigate against negative effects on agricultural production is to identify the most likely issues and envisage ways that farmers, industry, policy, and other stakeholders can prepare flexible guides for likely futures.

Around 10 % of Scotland's total agricultural area is used to grow arable crops, such as cereals, fruit and vegetables (Scottish Agricultural Census, 2021). In 2021, there were 13,253 arable farm holdings (crops and fallow) covering 588,801 hectares. Most of the arable land was used for cereal growing (73% of arable land) while horticultural crops accounted for a small proportion (9% of arable land).

In 2019, Scottish farmers produced around 6.55 million tonnes of arable and horticultural produce (Scottish Agriculture Tables – economic report, 2020). Barley accounted for 2.04 million tonnes (or 31%), with wheat and potato accounting for much of the rest (15% and 16%, respectively), and soft fruit accounting for <1%. In terms of value to the Scottish economy, the combined arable and horticultural output was around £1.1 billion (in 2019), with approx. one-third attributable to cereals (£408 M), one-quarter to potatoes (£250 M) and 13% to fruit crops (£144 M).

The productivity and end use of arable produce varies with supply and demand. The area, yield and quality of crops can vary due to land suitability, environmental conditions, and pests and diseases. Cereal farming profits can be particularly volatile due to their specialisation and vulnerability to global market prices, weather and supply. When support payments are excluded, over 60% of cereal farms and just under 80% of general cropping farms remain profitable, compared to 28% of farms across the agricultural sector.

The **overall aim** of this research is to work with agricultural stakeholders to explore what might happen to arable and horticultural production in Scotland in the future and by doing so, raise awareness, stimulate creative thinking, and gain insights about the influence between the social, economic and environmental drivers. By looking at past and present events, this exercise will help identify avenues which are robust, flexible but imperfect guides to unpredictable future events and prepare for and prevent future threats. The study is carried out in two stages, the first of which is reported here: the **objective** was to work with stakeholders to characterise and prioritise key threats to the sustainability of key Scottish agriculture sectors.

Technical approach

A participatory approach was adopted to horizon scan with stakeholders for threats to key industries in the Scottish agriculture sector (Kok et al., 2011). A survey was created for online consultation with stakeholders about the main risks to arable and horticulture production (**Figure 1**). Six categories of risk were identified, covering the Social, Technological, Economic, Environmental, and Political (STEEP) drivers of change as the first step for constructing plausible future scenarios (Duckett et al., 2017). These included: pests and disease; climate change; societal, political, economic; and technological (**Figure 1**). Within each category, potential drivers of risk were identified based on expert knowledge of the authors, their colleagues and the literature.

Survey participants were asked to score each driver in terms of the likelihood that the risks will arise and the potential severity of the impact using the following scales:

Likelihood Scale

- 1= Very unlikely, little or no chance of it happening.
- 2= Unlikely but could occur.
- 3 = Possible, but less than 50/50 chance.
- 4= Probable, more than 50/50 chance.
- 5= Probable, highly likely/certain to occur

Severity level

- 1= Negligible/very minor (temporary) effect
- 2= Small effect
- 3= Moderate effect
- 4= Major (Long term) effect
- 5= Permanent change

Survey participants were also given the option of adding “other” drivers and scoring these for likelihood and severity. The survey gathered basic data on participant age group, sector or area of expertise, type of farm (if a farmer) and approximate geographic location (**Appendix 1**). The proposed research and survey were subjected to ethics review by Hutton Ethics Committee (finalised on 12th July 2022) and RESAS (finalised on 10th August 2022).

The survey was distributed to stakeholders in the arable and horticulture sector through multiple routes:

- Industry events (Potatoes in Practice, 11th Aug 2022; Hutton Barley Away Days, 24th – 25th Oct 2022)
- News item on the James Hutton Institute website amplified through social media posts
- Direct emailing to existing contacts and collaborators
- Through e-newsletters of membership organisations (e.g. LEAF UK, SAC Association of Potato Producers, Soil Association Scotland, GWCT, NFUS)

An information sheet (**Appendix 2**) was supplied to potential participants together with a QR code and weblink to the online survey. The survey opened on 11th August 2022 and closed on 3rd December 2022. Data from the survey were downloaded, cleaned, and analysed with R software. Of 76 observations, 71 were valid observations and were used for analysis. To reflect accurately the likelihood and severity assigned to drivers by participants we treated the variables as ordinal and calculated the weighted average according to the level and observed frequency of the variable.

The results were presented to fruit industry stakeholders at the Scottish Society for Soft Fruit Research (16th Feb 2023) to gather feedback on the scenario question(s) that should be addressed and appropriate timescales for the second stage of the study.

Figure 1. Six categories of risk to agricultural production used in the online survey. Each category includes several drivers, and survey participants could add further drivers when completing the online form.

Pests and diseases	Severity level	Likelihood scale
Invasive species		
Resistance-breaking strains/genotypes		
Changing weather conditions		
Loss of pesticides		
Other: [free text]		

Societal	Severity level	Likelihood scale
Low labour availability		
Employment/wage regulations		
Dietary change by consumers		
Changing farming demographics		
Changing consumer demographics		
Other: [free text]		

Economic	Severity level	Likelihood scale
High input costs		
Export regulations		
Economic prosperity/Affordability to consumers		
Access to natural resources		
Globalisation/Trade across borders		
Retail sector developments		
Other: [free text]		

Climate	Severity level	Likelihood scale
Climate and pest and disease pressures		
Climate and water/nutrient stress		
Net zero carbon targets		
Future land use		
Other: [free text]		

Political	Severity level	Likelihood scale
Global instability		
EU exit		
Scottish independence		
Fiscal policy		
National and local agendas on food system governance		
Other: [free text]		

Technological	Severity level	Likelihood scale
Crop breeding advances		
Precision management tools		
Digitalisation availability/access		
Reduced waste/Circular economy		
Other: [free text]		

Results

The survey elicited 71 valid responses (August to December 2022) from arable, horticulture and both sectors. There were 36 responses from males and 22 from females, and the remaining 13 participants either preferred not to indicate gender or did not answer the question. Most of the desired stakeholder groups were represented (**Figure 2**), particularly scientific researchers, farmers, and public agencies; agronomists, marketing and policy were represented at a low level, while value chain industries were least well represented. Not all participants responded to all questions, therefore we analysed the data by risk category, as each category is an independent variable.

Figure 2. Representation across stakeholder groups amongst the online survey respondents.

Pests and disease drivers

Survey responses indicated that, on average, changing climatic conditions represent a highly likely and permanent threat to agricultural production, and loss of pesticides present a highly likely threat with long term effects (**Figure 3, red circle**). New invasive pests/pathogens and resistance-breaking genotypes/strains were also considered likely to arise and pose moderate threats.

'Other' drivers proposed by survey participants included soil degradation, loss of biodiversity and natural regulation services, and pollinator losses.

Figure 3. Weighted average values calculated from recorded online survey responses for the likelihood and severity of drivers of risk to Scottish agricultural production from pests and diseases.

Societal drivers

Low labour availability and changing farming demographics were considered as important threats to agricultural production, occurring with >50% probability and causing major long-term effects (**Figure 4, red circle**). Changing consumer demographics and dietary shifts were also considered to have major long-term effects along with wage regulation, although these were considered less likely to happen.

‘Other’ drivers proposed by survey participants included land use and demand for good agricultural land, skills shortages, consumer environmental concerns, retailer positions on pesticide use and product visual appearance, and a focus on nutrient density of food products.

Figure 4. Weighted average values calculated from recorded online survey responses for the likelihood and severity of societal drivers of risk to Scottish agricultural production.

Economic drivers

Increasing input costs were perceived to be highly likely and create major long term effects on agricultural production (**Figure 5, red arrow**). Changing export regulations and access to natural resources were considered moderately likely risks and with major or minor effects (respectively). Trade globalisation and product affordability (to consumers) were considered as moderately likely threats to agricultural production with significant effects, while retail sector developments were considered less likely and with smaller impacts.

‘Other’ drivers proposed by survey participants included consumer preferences, payments for ecosystem services, competition with imported products, energy/food price security, labour and production costs, and general profitability.

Figure 5. Weighted average values calculated from recorded online survey responses for the likelihood and severity of economic drivers of risk to Scottish agricultural production.

Climate change drivers

Climate change effects on pests and disease pressures and on plant nutrient stress were considered moderately likely with significant effects on agricultural production (**Figure 6**). Net Zero carbon targets for agriculture and the effects of the changing climate on land use were considered moderately likely risks but with smaller impacts.

‘Other’ drivers proposed by survey participants included extreme weather events and water shortages, extended growing seasons, and new crops.

Figure 6. Weighted average values calculated from recorded online survey responses for the likelihood and severity of climate change drivers of risk to Scottish agricultural production.

Political drivers

Participants considered that EU exit and global instability represented highly likely threats to arable and horticulture production with moderate-to-major long term impacts (**Figure 7, red circle**). Changes in fiscal policy and national/local food system governance were considered moderately likely to occur and with moderate-to-major impacts on agricultural production, while Scottish independence was scored similarly in terms of the potential impact, but was considered less likely to occur than the other drivers.

Figure 7. Weighted average values calculated from recorded online survey responses for the likelihood and severity of political drivers of risk to Scottish agricultural production.

'Other' drivers proposed by survey participants included agricultural/environmental regulations, regulatory divergence, policies to reduce offshoring of carbon emissions, and policies relating to natural assets.

Technological drivers

Participants considered that technological drivers of change from crop breeding advances, precision management tools, and digitalisation in agriculture were >50% likely to occur and were likely to have significant or moderate effects on agricultural production (**Figure 8**). Drivers to reduce waste and create a circular economy were considered moderately likely to occur and with moderate-to-major impacts on agricultural production.

'Other' drivers proposed by survey participants included use of robotics, adoption of regenerative agriculture, and new crops.

Figure 8. Weighted average values calculated from recorded online survey responses for the likelihood and severity of technological drivers of risk to Scottish agricultural production.

Conclusions

Analysis of results from an online survey gathering responses from 71 participants representing stakeholder groups across the arable and horticulture sectors has highlighted the priority drivers of risk to agricultural production. These can be summarised as follows:

- Changing climate conditions
- Increasing pest and disease pressures
- Loss of pesticides
- Labour and changing farming demographics
- High input costs
- EU exit and global instability
- Reducing waste, digitalisation and crop breeding

It should be noted that some of these drivers of risk might also present opportunities. For example, extended growing seasons could allow new crops to be grown, crop breeding advances could improve pest and disease resistance, or tolerance of extreme weather events, while efforts to reduce waste and increase efficiency could decrease input costs.

Next steps

The major drivers of change identified and prioritised by this study will be used to outline future likely scenarios of risks (and opportunities) with stakeholders using a participatory approach. Two workshops will be conducted (anticipated in early summer 2023) to analyse scenarios with stakeholders from arable and horticulture sectors to consider interim steps and strategies that can be adopted to deliver desirable endpoints. Actions for technical improvements, regulatory changes, and industry efficiencies to safeguard crop production and value chains under different scenarios will be summarised in a policy briefing.

Acknowledgements

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Threats to arable and horticulture production in Scotland.

Thank you for participating in this research, your contribution is very important.

Your participation will help us to identify major risks to Scottish arable and horticulture production. The information will be used to characterise scenarios of threats to agricultural production and determine how agriculture and policy might prepare in advance for future risks.

This research consists of two stages. Stage one is this 10 minute survey. Stage two is the participation in a workshop and interviews. You can voluntarily participate in one or both stages of the project as participation in one stage does not depend on your participation in the other.

Please state:

- Continue with survey [go to next page]

- I do not want to fill the survey now, but I agree to be contacted at a later date. Please enter your contact details here _____
Your response ensures we have your consent to participate in the research and store your contact details for the project duration (end of March 2024).

Privacy notice:

This is an anonymous survey and we do not intend to collect any names or other identifying information through survey responses. If you wish to be contacted for participating in future stages of this project such as workshops and interviews and therefore share your contact details, we will treat this information as confidential and will be used only for inviting you to further stages of the research. Your contact details will be stored separately from your survey responses. Only authorised members of the research team will have access to this information. The James Hutton Institute (“Hutton”, “us” or “we”) will be a data controller over your personal data and will use this data only for the purposes of the research undertaken in this project “threats to arable and horticulture production in Scotland”. The anonymised dataset will be maintained for a minimum of 10 years after the project ends.; when published, the anonymised dataset will be assigned a licence that maximises accessibility. Further information about how Hutton processes your personal data and what your rights are in relation to your data can be found at our full privacy notice, www.hutton.ac.uk/terms; or, if you have any queries about your personal data, you can contact our Data Protection Officer on dpo@hutton.ac.uk. If you would like to know more about this research please contact maria.lozada@hutton.ac.uk

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Your participation in this 10 minute survey is voluntary. If you decide to participate in this survey, you may withdraw at any time.

The project is carried out by the James Hutton Institute for which it received funding from Scottish Government's Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services (RESAS) project A1-2-B on Epidemiology of Pests and Diseases.

Characteristics.

Please feel free to use "I prefer not to answer" at any time.

1.- Age group:

- Younger than 35 yrs.
- 35-50 yrs.
- 51-65 yrs.
- 66 yrs. or older
- I prefer not to answer

2. Gender

- Male
- Female
- Prefer to self-describe: _____
- I prefer not to answer

Please indicate participant group that best describes you: [depending on the type of stakeholder the survey will continue differently]

- Farmer
- Agroindustry/ processors
- Marketing
- Adviser/agronomist
- Policy maker
- Public agency
- Researcher
- Other: _____

- I prefer not to answer

[If farmers]

2. What is your production, please indicate.

- Arable
- Horticulture
- Arable and horticulture
- I prefer not to answer

3. What is your main farming system, please indicate.

- Conventional
- Organic
- Agroecological
- Regenerative
- A combination, please indicate _____
- Other _____

3. Where is your farm located?

Please enter the first half of your postcode _____

[If other type of stakeholders]

What is your area of expertise? Please specify: _____

Severity and likelihood Scores

Instructions for participants:

You will find six main categories of drivers that represent potential threats to arable and horticulture production. We kindly ask you to score these categories according to how, in your experience and knowledge, these drivers may represent a risk to agricultural production.

Pest and Diseases

Can you please score the following categories?

Please add any other category that you think is important and has not been mentioned.

Pests and diseases	Severity level	Likelihood scale
Invasive species		
Resistance-breaking strains/genotypes		
Changing weather conditions		
Loss of pesticides		
Other: [free text]		

Societal

Can you please score the following categories?

Please add any other category that you think is important and has not been mentioned.

Societal	Severity level	Likelihood scale

Low labour availability		
Employment/wage regulations		
Dietary change by consumers		
Changing farming demographics		
Changing consumer demographics		
Other: [free text]		

Economic

Can you please score the following categories?

Please add any other category that you think is important and has not been mentioned.

Economic	Severity level	Likelihood scale
High input costs		
Export regulations		
Economic prosperity/Affordability to consumers		
Access to natural resources		
Globalisation/Trade across borders		
Retail sector developments		
Other: [free text]		

Climate

Can you please score the following categories?

Please add any other category that you think is important and has not been mentioned.

Climate	Severity level	Likelihood scale
Climate and pest and disease pressures		
Climate and water/nutrient stress		
Net zero carbon targets		
Future land use		
Other: [free text]		

Political

Can you please score the following categories?

Please add any other category that you think is important and has not been mentioned.

Political	Severity level	Likelihood scale
Global instability		
EU exit		
Scottish independence		
Fiscal policy		
National and local agendas on food system governance		

Other: [free text]

Technological

Can you please score the following categories?

Please add any other category that you think is important and has not been mentioned.

Technological	Severity level	Likelihood scale
Crop breeding advances		
Precision management tools		
Digitalisation availability/access		
Reduced waste/Circular economy		
Other: [free text]		

Would you like to add any comments?

As mentioned, this is the first stage of the research. A second stage will be based on workshops and interviews. If you would like to be contacted for voluntary participation in the second stage of this research, please enter your contact details below. Your personal details will be treated with confidentiality.

Contact details _____

If you know someone who would like to participate please forward the link (copy and paste)

For more information about this research, please send an email to maria.lozada@hutton.ac.uk

**THANK YOU VERY MUCH FOR YOUR TIME AND HELP IN THIS RESEARCH.
YOUR INPUT IS ESSENTIAL FOR US.**

What will affect the future resilience of Scottish arable and horticulture production?

The changing climate, pest and disease pressures, and global events can affect the productivity of agriculture and trade in agricultural goods. One way to mitigate against negative effects on agricultural production is to identify the most likely issues and envisage ways that farmers, industry, policy, and other stakeholders can prepare for the future.

Your help is vital: We need farmers, agronomists, processors, retailers, policy advisors and researchers to identify and prioritise the main issues affecting arable and horticultural production in Scotland now and in the future.

We kindly request 10 minutes of your time to complete a simple survey. The survey can be completed online by scanning the QR code below.

We will use the information from the survey to prioritise major threats to arable and horticulture production and their likely impacts. This information will be used in the next phase of our research to characterise future scenarios and how to mitigate against negative impacts. This will involve a workshop and follow-up interviews where your input will be welcomed.

This research is carried out by the James Hutton Institute for which it receives funding from Scottish Government's Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services (RESAS) project A1-2-B (Epidemiology of Pests and Diseases).

Threats to arable and horticulture production in Scotland: further information

About this research. This research is about understanding threats to arable and horticulture production in Scotland. The changing climate, pest and disease pressures, and global events can affect the productivity of agriculture and trade in agricultural goods. One way to mitigate against negative effects on agricultural production is to identify the most likely threats and envisage ways that farmers and other stakeholders can prepare for the future. This project will characterise, prioritise and analyse future scenarios and co-construct solutions with stakeholders. The project is carried out by Luz Maria Lozada and Alison Karley, scientists at the James Hutton Institute. The project receives funding from Scottish Government's Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services (RESAS) project A1-2-B on Epidemiology of Pests and Diseases.

Why should I participate? Your participation is very valuable for this research. This research will help with understanding the main threats to sustainability of key agricultural sectors in Scotland by characterising likely scenarios and analysing them with stakeholders. The scenarios will be discussed with stakeholders in a workshop later in the year to identify potential mitigations. The information you provide will be used to determine how agriculture and policy might prepare in advance for future threats to agricultural production.

Research Approach This research consists of two stages. Stage one is this 10-minute survey. Stage two is the participation in a workshop and follow-up interviews. You can voluntarily participate in one or both stages of the project as participation in one stage does not commit you to participating in the other. Your participation in this short survey will help us to identify major risks to Scottish arable and horticultural production.

Data analysis and confidentiality: what will happen to the data I provide? All data you provide will be treated as confidential. You will not be identifiable in any research publications and outputs resulting from this study. Only Hutton researchers will have access to raw data. It will not be shared and, to avoid unintended disclosure, data will be imported to a password-protected excel file, stored on a secure network server. Anonymised data will be reported in the outputs of this project. Your personal data will not be shared at any time. All responses will be anonymised and nothing in the research outputs will make you identifiable. The anonymised dataset will be maintained for a minimum of 10 years after the project ends. When published, the anonymised dataset will be assigned a licence that maximises accessibility, as required by the funder.

Do I have to take part? Your participation is voluntary, and you can withdraw at any time. If you would like to withdraw, please contact maria.lozada@hutton.ac.uk. The data you provide will be withdrawn before analysis, but once anonymised and/or published it cannot be withdrawn. There are no incentives for participating in this study.

Are there any possible risks from taking part? There are no risks from taking part in this research as any confidential information will be anonymised.

Further questions and who to contact:

If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to contact us:

Luz Maria Lozada maría.lozada@hutton.ac.uk and Ali Karley ali.karley@hutton.ac.uk

For further information, including independent data protection advice and information in relation to your rights, you can contact the Information Commissioner:

The Information Commissioner, Wycliffe House, Water Lane, Wilmslow, Cheshire, SK9 5AF

Tel: 0303 123 1113 Website: www.ico.org.uk

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